

Removal of copper from aqueous solution using eggshell as an adsorbent

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Abstract : Hen eggshell powder has been found to be a potential adsorbent for the removal of copper from aqueous medium. A detailed adsorption study of Cu^{II} on eggshell powder was investigated. Batch adsorption study was carried out as a function of solute concentration, contact time, adsorbent dose, pH and temperature. The experimental data were analysed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. It was found that these two isotherm models fitted well. pH variation study revealed that the adsorption increased with the increase in pH of the solution. Maximum uptake of Cu^{II} from the solution by the eggshell was found to be 51.67 mg g^{-1} at 6 mg L^{-1} of initial Cu^{II} concentration. Adsorption data were analyzed using kinetic models, Lagergren's first order and pseudo second order. It was observed that pseudo second order represented the best correlation. Thermodynamic study revealed that the sorption of Cu^{II} by hen eggshell powder is an endothermic process showing increase in sorption at higher temperatures. The negative values of standard free energy (ΔG°) indicate the spontaneity of the sorption process. The present investigation emphasizes that eggshell powder may be utilized as an efficient material for the removal of Cu^{II} from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Copper, adsorbent, eggshell, Langmuir isotherms, Freundlich isotherms.

Introduction

The term "heavy metal" although not rigidly defined is commonly held for those metals which have specific weights more than 5 g cm^{-3} . These metals are found in abundance in rock formations. Anthropogenic contribution of heavy metals in the biosphere is industrialization and urbanization. Release of heavy metals such as Cr, Ni, Cd, and Cu from industrial wastewater into the aquatic system is a major environmental concern. Waste water irrigation enhances the heavy metal content of the soils. Among pollutants, heavy metals create several threats to biosphere due to their property of bioaccumulation in different trophic levels of the ecosystem¹. These heavy metals enter into the urban water system causing health problems.

Copper is one of the major contaminants emanating from electrical, electroplating and metal finishing industries. It is often found in high concentrations near mines, landfills and waste disposal sites. In humans, intake of excessively large doses of copper leads to severe mucosal irritation and corrosion, widespread capillary damage, hepatic and renal damage and central nervous system irrita-

tion followed by depression². Inhalation of copper spray increases the risk of lung cancer among exposed workers³. Maximum permissible concentrations of copper in drinking water by World Health Organisation (WHO), United State Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) are 1-2 and 1-3 mg L^{-1} , respectively⁴. The permissible level of copper for industrial waste water to be discharged to the surface water is 3 mg L^{-1} ⁵. Hence, the removal of copper from wastewater before its discharge into the aquatic system is extremely important and deserves immediate attention.

Hen eggshell is an unavoidable waste material which mainly contains calcium carbonate and proteins. As the percentage of calcium carbonate in hen eggshell is about 94%, therefore its behaviour should be similar to sorbents that contain this compound i.e. calcite⁶ and calcareous soil⁷. The present paper investigates in detail the adsorption of copper by hen eggshell powder in simulated waste water from the equilibrium, kinetic and thermodynamic angles. Large amounts of eggshells are produced in some countries, such as the United States in which annually 120,000 tonnes of waste eggshells are

generated and disposed in landfills⁸. This also creates a serious problem for egg processing industries due to stricter environmental regulations and high landfill costs⁹. Therefore, in this paper, light has been thrown to promote eggshells as an easily available porous adsorbent.

The objective of the work presented in this paper is to undertake an adsorption analysis of the heavy metal copper on eggshell.

Detailed adsorption study of Cu^{II} on hen eggshell was investigated. Batch adsorption study was carried out as a function of contact time, adsorbent dose, temperature (30–50° C). The experimental data were analysed using Langmuir¹⁰ and Freundlich¹¹ isotherm models.

Results and discussion

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Fig. 1 shows the adsorption of Cu^{II} with varying weights of the adsorbent (0.1–2 g). The result shows that the uptake of Cu is the most at 0.4 g of the adsorbent. The adsorbent dose of 0.4 g was able to adsorb 98.6% Cu^{II} from 100 mL of 6.0 mg L^{-1} Cu^{II} solution. This high

Fig. 1. Adsorption profile of Cu^{II} as a function of varying adsorbent dose (Time = 30 min, $C_i = 6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, pH = 7).

percentage of Cu^{II} removal may be attributed to the active site of the adsorbent surface. The percentage removal decreases as the dosage is increased beyond 0.4 g. A possible reason for the decrease can be attributed to the fact that higher doses cause particles to aggregate, overlap and overcrowd resulting in the decrease of the availability of the surface area as well as decrease in the sorption capacity.

Effect of pH :

Fig. 2 portrays the adsorption of Cu^{II} with varying pH of solutions. It is observed from the figure that the maximum removal of the Cu^{II} ions take place at pH 7. The initial pH significantly affects the metal-solution,

Fig. 2. Adsorption profile of Cu^{II} as a function of varying pH (Time = 30 min, $C_i = 6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

adsorbent-surface and hence the sorption of heavy metal ions. As can be seen in the figure, below pH 2, the removal of Cu^{II} ions diminishes as because CaCO_3 and MgCO_3 dissolve in the presence of acids thereby hindering the sorption of copper ions due to less availability of adsorption sites. Above pH 2, the removal efficiency increases, reaching a maximum value over the pH range 6–9 followed by a decrease. The low removal of the Cu^{II} ions at pH value < 5 may be attributed to a possible ion-exchange mechanism between Cu^{II} ions and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ with calcium (CaCO_3) present on the surface of eggshell in a similar manner as mentioned in reference¹². The enhanced removal of the metal ion as the solution pH is increased (more than 5) can be attributed to the adsorption of hydrolytic products^{13,14} and/or surface precipitation of the metal as colloidal insoluble hydroxides, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, forming successive layers on the sorbent surface¹⁵.

Most metal cations are removed by (i) adsorption on solid phases via precipitation of their insoluble hydroxides, (ii) ion exchange, (iii) flocculation by adsorption of hydrolytic product and (iv) complexation with specific surface sites, provided the appropriate conditions prevail^{15,16}. As a function of solution pH¹⁷, the copper(II) species may exist as $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{OH})_2^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_3^-$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_4^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{OCu})_{n-2}\text{OCu}]^+$ soluble hydrolytic species in addition to the insoluble colloidal copper hydroxide $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2(\text{s})$. The powdered eggshell consists mainly of calcite (CaCO_3). When calcite is suspended with water, HCO_3^- , Ca^{2+} , CaHCO_3^+ and CaHO^+ are formed as surface-charged species and their presence is a function of solution pH¹⁸. Moreover, OH^- , H^+ and HCO_3^- are considered as potential determining ions in addition to Ca^{2+} and CaCO_3 . The dissociation of these groups leads to an acidic or alkaline surface (positive or negative surface charge). These findings were confirmed practically by stirring the eggshell sorbent with distilled water

for 1 h after which the suspension pH decreases. This may be attributed to desorption of H⁺ ions from sorbent surface or sorption of OH⁻ ions from the solution which agree with the literature data¹⁹. Therefore, the proposed mechanism may occur as follows; at pH < 5, the removal of the Cu^{II} ions may be attributed to a possible ion-exchange mechanism between Cu^{II} ions and calcium containing eggshell in a similar manner to that reported earlier. Also, adsorption may take place through precipitation of copper carbonate on eggshell surface according to the following equations²⁰ :

In the pH range 6–9, where the maximal removal of Cu²⁺ ions occurred, adsorption may have taken place via hydrogen bonding and surface precipitation of the metal as colloidal insoluble hydroxides, Cu(OH)₂(s), forming successive layers on the sorbent surface¹⁶. In alkaline medium, at pH > 9, the removal of Cu^{II} ions decreases, which may be attributed to the incapability of adsorption of the negative species Cu(OH)₃⁻ and Cu(OH)₄²⁻ on the negative surface of eggshell sorbent.

As eggshell is mainly composed of CaCO₃, it is expected that any aqueous solution equilibrated with eggshell became more basic and this is confirmed by following mechanism²¹.

Hydrolysis reaction of CaCO₃ gives a basic solution because Ca²⁺ and OH⁻ increase the pH of the solution. It is this bond breaking that produces heat. Calcium hydroxide is not very soluble so it is soon saturated and forms a solid.

The decrease in the removal efficiency at pH values >9 may be attributed to the fact that the intermediate negative species of copper, Cu(OH)₃⁻ and Cu(OH)₄²⁻ which are formed at higher pH's are incapable of combining with the negative surface of the eggshell due to repulsion between like charges. Therefore, pH 7 was maintained throughout all other experiments.

Effect of temperature :

The effect of temperature was studied in the temperature range of 30–50 °C using 0.4 g eggshell as an adsor-

bent dose, pH 7 and an initial concentration of 6 mg L⁻¹ and the study has been depicted in Fig. 3. It is seen that the percentage removal increases with the increase in temperature and the q_{max} values are maximum at 50 °C at almost 52 mg g⁻¹. Calcium carbonate is unusual in that its solubility increases with decreasing temperature. Hence, there is a lesser availability of adsorbent sites at lower temperatures and so the mobility of Cu^{II} ions from the bulk solution towards the adsorbent surface at higher temperatures is greatly favoured. This agrees well with the literature data^{22,23}. Thus, 50 °C has been fixed as equilibrium temperature for further experiments.

Fig. 3. Adsorption profile of Cu^{II} as a function of varying temperature (Time = 30 min, C_i = 6 mg L⁻¹)

Effect of time :

The effect of the contact time for the adsorption of Cu^{II} was studied for a period of 60 min with evaluation after every 10 min for an initial concentration of 6 mg L⁻¹ at pH 7. It is observed from Fig. 4 that the optimum time for the equilibrium concentration to be reached is 60 min, after which desorption increases and the percentage removal decreases. The data depicted in this figure indicate that the adsorption of the copper ions is quite rapid at the

Fig. 4. Adsorption profile of Cu^{II} as a function of varying time (C_i = 6 mg L⁻¹, pH = 7, Temp = 50 °C).

initial stages, which may suggest that adsorption occurs mainly at the surface of the solid sorbent and to some extent at the internal macro-pores, transitional pores and micropores^{24,25}. However, with the passage of time, the rate of adsorption decreases owing to the decrease in the rate of diffusion of the copper ions through the pores²⁶, and ultimately reaches a constant value (equilibrium time). From the results obtained it is found that a 60 min of stirring time is required for equilibrium to set in and this time has been maintained for future experiments.

Isotherm models :

Models play a key role in transferring technologies from the laboratories to a full-scale application. Good models cannot only help in analyzing the experimental data but also help in predicting the response of the systems to changing conditions. The obtained experimental equilibrium data for the adsorption of Cu²⁺ by eggshell at different temperatures 30 °C, 40 °C, and 50 °C are presented as Langmuir isotherms in Fig. 5 and Freundlich isotherms in Fig. 6. The adsorption isotherms were measured at a constant initial pH 7 and a concentration range of 6–14 mg L⁻¹.

The Langmuir adsorption isotherm and the Freundlich

Fig. 5. Langmuir adsorption isotherm profiles of Cu^{II} at different temperatures.

Fig. 6. Freundlich adsorption isotherm profiles of Cu^{II} at different temperatures.

adsorption isotherm equations are given as eqs. (3) and (4) respectively :

$$1/q_e = (1/bq_{max}) 1/C_e + 1/q_{max} \quad (3)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of Cu^{II} ions remaining in the solution and q_e is the amount of Cu^{II} ions adsorbed per unit mass of eggshell. The Langmuir equilibrium constants q_{max} and b in eq.(3) are quantities describing the adsorption process, where q_{max} is related to the retention capacity of the adsorbent and b is related to the binding energy between the adsorbent and the adsorbate.

The Freundlich isotherm model in the linearised form is given as below :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \quad (4)$$

where n relates to affinity and K_f to adsorption capacity and are Freundlich constants.

The data obtained have a great fitting to both the isotherm models as both display high correlation coefficients (R^2) values at 0.9 as featured in Table 1. Hence there exists a possibility of a monolayer adsorption onto a homogeneous surface with a finite number of active sites according to the Langmuir theory as well as a possibility of a heterogeneous adsorption surface projecting multi-layer adsorption on account of the Freundlich isotherm theory. The Langmuir constants b and q_{max} are evaluated from the slopes and intercepts of the straight lines in Fig. 5.

Table 1. Isotherm parameters of Cu^{II} on eggshell powder

Isotherm	Constants	Temp. (K)		
		303	313	323
Langmuir	b (L mg ⁻¹)	0.382	0.141	0.130
	Q_{max} (mg g ⁻¹)	17.61	46.92	51.67
Freundlich	R^2	0.992	0.987	0.993
	n	1.20	1.10	1.08
	K_f	1.50	1.57	1.59
	R^2	0.985	0.981	0.989

Adsorption kinetics study :

The prediction of adsorption rate gives important information for designing batch adsorption systems. Information on the kinetics of solute uptake is required for selecting optimum operating conditions for full-scale batch processes. The kinetics of the adsorption data were ana-

lyzed using the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic model. These models correlate solute uptake, which are important in predicting the reactor volume.

Lagergren's first order model is represented by the equation,

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - k_1 t / 2.303 \quad (5)$$

where q_e is the amount of adsorbed Cu^{II} onto the eggshell powder at equilibrium (mg g^{-1}), q_t is the amount of Cu^{II} adsorbed at time t and k_1 is the first order rate constant. The plot of $\log (q_e - q_t)$ versus t in Fig. 7 reveals that the kinetic data of adsorption of Cu on eggshell powder and the results are tabulated in Table 2.

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log (q_e - q_t)$ vs t .

Table 2. Rate constant of kinetic study of Cu^{II} adsorption onto eggshell powder

Model type	Constant of pseudo reaction q_e (mg/g)	R^2
Pseudo-first order	$k_1 = 0.0774 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.978
Pseudo-second order	$k_2 = 0.5708 \text{ g mg}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.999

Lagergren's second order rate equation in the linearised form is

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + t/q_e \quad (6)$$

The plot of t/q_t against t in Fig. 8 represents the kinetic data of adsorption of Cu^{II} on eggshell. The process kinetics shows a remarkable fitting to the second order rate equation with $R^2 = 0.999$. The second order rate constant k_2 is determined from the intercept of the graph and the result shown in Table 2 below.

Thermodynamic study :

The thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of copper ions by eggshell such as the enthalpy change (ΔH°), the Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) and the entropy change (ΔS°) can be calculated using the following basic thermodynamic relations²⁷.

Fig. 8. Plot of t/q_t vs t .

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_c \quad (7)$$

$$\ln K_c = \Delta S^\circ / R - \Delta H^\circ / RT \quad (8)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, $8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, T is the absolute solution temperature and K_c is the equilibrium constant calculated as q_e/C_e . The plot of $\ln K_c$ vs $1/T$, Fig. 9 gives the straight line from which ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated from the slope and intercept of the linearised form. The results are arranged in Table 3.

Fig. 9. Plot of $\ln K_c$ vs $1/T$.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of Cu^{II} adsorption onto eggshell powder

T (K)	ΔG° (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH° (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS° ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)
303	-4.42293	4.055503	28.08235
313	-4.77786		
323	-4.98657		
		Mean value	

The negative value of ΔG° confirms the spontaneity of the adsorption process with increasing temperature and the positive value of ΔH° suggests that the adsorption is endothermic in nature. The positive ΔS° interprets the increased randomness at the solid-solution interface.

Experimental

Preparation of eggshell powder :

Eggshells of poultry chickens were thoroughly cleaned with de-ionized water and dried in a microwave oven for 60 min at 100 °C. It was then cooled and powdered in a mixer grinder and sieved through 100 μm sieve. The powder was washed with double distilled water for three times and dried for 60 min at 100 °C in a microwave oven. The powder was then stored in an air tight container ready for use.

Reagents :

Analytical grade $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used to make the stock solution of Cu^{II} (1000 mg L^{-1}) in de-ionized water. The stock solution was diluted by serial dilution method as required.

Batch adsorption experiments :

Adsorption experiments were carried out in batches of 100 mL of 6.0 mg L^{-1} of Cu^{II} solution with known weights of eggshell powder. The solutions were shaken in a mechanical shaker for a definite period of time. It was then filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 42 and the Cu^{II} concentration was measured before and after adsorption by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL 4141). Adsorption parameters such as adsorbent dose, shaking time were optimized by the method of continuous variation. The optimized parameters were found to be 0.4 g of adsorbent dose and 1 hour of contact time and 50 °C temperature to reach equilibrium for 6 mg L^{-1} of Cu^{II} concentration. The adsorption of Cu^{II} by the walls of the glass vessel and the filter paper have been ignored while determining the optimal conditions of the adsorption process. However, the mean of triplicated experimental data have been reported for the equilibrium, kinetic and thermodynamic studies.

The removal efficiency²⁸ of the iron solution was calculated from the equation

$$\% \text{ Removal} = \frac{C_i - C_f}{C_i} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

where C_i and C_f are the initial and final concentration of copper in solution in (mg L^{-1}) respectively.

The sorption capacity²⁹ of Cu^{II} solution is the concentration of Cu^{II} adsorbed on the eggshell powder and can be calculated with the help of the balance principle

$$q = \frac{V(C_i - C_f)}{m} \quad (10)$$

where V is the volume of the solution in (ml) and m is the weight of the adsorbent (g).

pH variation study :

To study the influence of pH on adsorption, the batch experiments were carried out in the pH range of (2.0–10.0). pH of the solution was adjusted using dilute NaOH and HCl.

Time variation study :

Adsorption behavior of Cu^{II} on eggshell powder was studied for eighty minutes with measurement taken after every 10 min.

Temperature variation study :

Adsorption of Cu^{II} on eggshell powder was studied as a function of temperature variation at 5 different temperatures 30 °C, 35 °C, 40 °C, 45 °C and 50 °C.

Conclusions :

The present study shows that the eggshell powder is an effective biosorbent for the adsorption of copper ions from aqueous solution. The biosorption capacity of eggshell powder is superior due to the higher content of carbonate groups. The effects of process parameters like pH, metal ion concentration, adsorbent concentration and adsorbent size on process equilibrium were studied. Study revealed that a maximum Cu^{II} removal of 96.47% could be achieved at pH 7 at 50 °C. The maximum loading capacity q_{max} was found to be 17.6, 46.9, 51.6 mg g^{-1} at pH 7 at temperatures 30 °C, 40 °C, 50 °C respectively. The adsorption isotherms could be well fitted by the Langmuir as well as by the Freundlich equation. The biosorption process could be best described by the second-order rate equation. The negative value of ΔG° and the positive value of ΔH° obtained confirm that the Cu^{II} adsorption is a spontaneous and endothermic process.

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